

Transport Properties and Local Ions Dynamics in LAMP-Based Hybrid Solid Electrolytes

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Hybrid solid electrolytes (HSEs), namely mixtures of polymer and inorganic electrolytes, have supposedly improved properties with respect to inorganic and polymer electrolytes. In practice, HSEs often show ionic conductivity below expectations, as the high interface resistance limits the contribution of inorganic electrolyte particles to the charge transport process. In this study, the transport properties of a series of HSEs containing $\text{Li}_{(1+x)}\text{Al}_x\text{Ti}_{(2-x)}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LAMP) as Li^+ -conducting filler are analyzed. The occurrence of Li^+ exchange across the two phases is proved by isotope exchange experiment, coupled with $^6\text{Li}/^7\text{Li}$ nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), and by 2D ^6Li exchange spectroscopy (EXSY), which gives a time constant for Li^+ exchange of about 50 ms at 60 °C. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) distinguishes a short-range and a long-range conductivity, the latter decreasing with LAMP concentration. LAMP particles contribute to the overall conductivity only at high temperatures and at high LAMP concentrations. Pulsed field gradient (PFG)-NMR suggests a selective decrease of the anions' diffusivity at high temperatures, translating into a marginal increase of the Li^+ transference number. Although the transport properties are only marginally affected, addition of moderate amounts of LAMP to polymer electrolytes enhances their mechanical properties, thus improving the plating/stripping performance and processability.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are the principal element for electrochemical energy storage in portable electronics and automotive applications. LIBs are characterized by high energy density (260 Wh kg^{-1} , 700 Wh L^{-1} at cell level),^[1] which is, however, still insufficient to meet the targets of driving range in full battery electric vehicles (> 300 Wh kg^{-1} , > 800 Wh L^{-1} at cell level).^[2] Higher values of energy density can be obtained by substituting the conventional graphite anode with a high-capacity lithium metal anode (372 mAh g^{-1} vs 3860 mAh g^{-1} for graphite and lithium metal, respectively). This, in turn, leads to serious safety concerns, owing to the growth of lithium dendrites, which can cause short circuits and thermal runaway, and are particularly dangerous in combination with common flammable liquid battery electrolytes.^[3] A possible solution to this issue involves the adoption of nonflammable solid-state electrolytes (SSEs), such as inorganic ceramic

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electrolytes (IEs)^[4] and polymer electrolytes (PEs).^[5] IEs have high ionic conductivity but are affected by unfavorable mechanical properties (oxides) or electrochemical stability (sulfides). On the contrary, PEs have better flexibility and processability, but have also low ionic conductivity, preventing their use at room temperature.^[6] Composite polymer electrolytes (CPEs), that is polymer electrolytes containing inorganic particles,^[7] have shown improved mechanical and transport properties with respect to pristine PEs. The role of inorganic fillers in modulating the transport properties of polymer electrolytes has been known for a long time. Nanometer-sized non-conductive (passive) fillers, such as Al₂O₃ and TiO₂, were found to increase the ionic conductivity and lithium-ion transference number of polyether-based polymer electrolytes.^[8–12] This was attributed to an increased lithium-ion mobility and lower polymer crystallinity, thanks also to the Lewis acid–base interactions between the filler acid surface groups and the polyether oxygens.

In recent years, the interest has shifted towards the use of Li⁺-conducting (active) fillers. CPEs containing Li⁺-conducting fillers are also known as hybrid solid electrolytes (HSEs), that is, mixed inorganic-polymer ionic conductors.^[13] Strictly speaking, HSEs can be classified as CPEs, but to distinguish between those CPEs with passive fillers and those with active fillers, having conceptually different charge transport mechanism, we will refer to the latter as HSEs. HSEs are considered as one of the most promising classes of solid-state electrolytes for lithium battery applications,^[13] as they supposedly show benefits with respect to both IEs and PEs, such as higher flexibility than IEs and improved transport properties compared to PEs.^[6] Typical active fillers used in HSEs include garnet-type oxides,^[14–19] sulfides,^[20,21] and NASICON-type phosphates,^[22–32] such as Li_(1+x)Al_xGe_(2-x)(PO₄)₃ (LAGP) and Li_(1+x)Al_xTi_(2-x)(PO₄)₃ (LATP). The latter is particularly interesting owing to its low cost (with respect to LAGP), its relatively high ionic conductivity and stability under ambient conditions,^[33] what makes LATP appealing also in terms of processability. Furthermore, the surface of LATP is considerably less reactive than that of garnet- and sulfide-based fillers. High reactivity of the filler surface groups can prompt incompatibility issues within the HSE leading to partial degradation of the polymer host matrix.^[34–36]

Several studies reported an increase of the ionic conductivity in HSEs containing NASICON-filler particles, compared to pristine polymer electrolytes.^[34,37–39] This effect was ascribed either to the formation of a highly conductive amorphous polymer phase at the polymer/particles interface,^[8,40] or to the presence of space charge layers and oxygen vacancies at the particles surface, providing fast additional conduction pathways for Li⁺.^[41,42] For instance, Wang et al. observed an increase of the ionic conductivity in LATP/PEO (polyethylene oxide)/LiClO₄-based HSEs, up to

15 wt% LATP, and attributed it to a decrease of the PEO crystallinity and to an increase of the charge carrier concentration.^[40] Wang et al. attributed the increase in conductivity, in PEO/LATP HSEs, to the formation of a highly conductive polymer interlayer surrounding the LATP particles. On the contrary, at very high LATP concentrations, particles agglomeration results in a decrease of the ionic conductivity.^[37] Wu et al. studied the Li⁺ distribution and conduction mechanism in HSEs based on PEO and NASICON-type LiZr₂(PO₄)₃.^[29] Also in this case, the higher ionic conductivity of the HSEs was attributed to the presence of localized amorphous polymer domains in proximity of the filler particles, characterized by lower association between Li⁺ and the PEO ether oxygens, and thus by higher cations mobility. Furthermore, the hybrid electrolytes showed higher lithium transference number, attributed to the interactions between TFSI⁻ anions and the filler particles. In all these previous cases, the enhancement of the transport properties was related to the formation of a highly conductive, disordered environment in the polymer matrix, around the filler particles. This effect is especially important in HSEs composed of semicrystalline polymer matrices, such as PEO.

In the case of amorphous polymer matrices, the effect of Li⁺-conducting ceramic fillers on the transport properties and the overall conduction mechanism are less understood. With NASICON-type fillers, there are conflicting reports regarding the effect on the ionic conductivity. For instance, Liu and co-workers reported higher conductivity for plasticized HSEs based on PEO, LAGP and succinonitrile, compared to polymer electrolytes without LAGP.^[22] The enhancement was ascribed to the presence of the plasticizer facilitating the Li⁺ exchange between LAGP and the polymer matrix, therefore enabling the participation of the ceramic particles in the long-range charge transport. On the contrary, Trevisanello et al. observed no beneficial effect of LATP in HSEs with an amorphous polymer electrolyte.^[12]

In general, the interface resistance for the Li⁺ transport across the particle/polymer interface seemingly represents the limiting factor for overall charge transport process in HSEs.^[43] Other important elements affecting the performance of the electrolytes are the presence of ion pairs in the polymer electrolyte, the cation transference number and the electrolyte oxidative stability. These are possibly influenced by the presence of the filler, and particularly by local interactions between the polymer electrolyte components (polymer chains, cations, anions) and the particles surface, e.g. through Lewis acid-base interactions. Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is a powerful tool for the investigation of ions' diffusivity and chemical interactions, and has been recently used in the study of the conduction mechanism of HSEs.^[14,19,20,44–47] All these aspects, long-range charge and mass transport properties, and local chemical interactions, need to be understood to fully reveal the conduction mechanism in HSEs, and to assess the real contribution of Li⁺-conducting fillers in HSEs.

Herein, we examine the thermal, mechanical, transport properties and local ions dynamics of a family of highly conductive HSEs, based on a plasticized and amorphous polymer electrolyte matrix and micrometer-sized LATP particles. The ionic conductivity of the HSEs was studied by EIS. Analysis of the admittance spectra showed two different conductivities, namely a local conductivity and a long-range conductivity, the latter including the contribution of the particles' interface resistance. In addition, the

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Table 1. Density and composition of the four analyzed HSEs.

Sample	ρ [g cm ⁻³]	f_{LATP} [g g ⁻¹]	f_{LATP} [v/v]	$C_{\text{Li,LATP}}$ [mol L ⁻¹]	C_{LiTFSI} [mol L ⁻¹]
HSE-00	1.24	0	0	0	1.19
HSE-05	1.43	0.12	0.06	0.58	1.21
HSE-10	1.64	0.22	0.13	1.23	1.23
HSE-20	1.64	0.39	0.23	2.17	0.96

ions' diffusivity was investigated by pulsed-field gradient NMR (PFG-NMR), which revealed the effect of the filler particles on the transference numbers. Ion pairing effects, possibly resulting from the interaction of the anions with the filler particles surface, were evaluated by comparing the diffusivity data by NMR with those calculated from the ionic conductivity. The local ion dynamics and possible ions' interaction with the filler particles were further investigated in detail by solid-state NMR. Finally, the participation of LATP particles in the charge transport process was probed by solid-state NMR coupled with ⁶Li/⁷Li electrochemically driven isotope-exchange as well as by 2D NMR exchange spectroscopy (EXSY) technique.

Overall, this study provides a complete picture of the conduction mechanism in LATP-containing HSEs, that may pave the way towards a rational design of HSEs with tunable conducting properties.

2. Results and Discussion

Four hybrid solid electrolytes (HSEs), with LATP volumetric concentration varying from 0 to 20 vol%, were prepared and analyzed. Their density and composition, with respect to the salt and LATP concentrations, are shown in **Table 1**. A slight increase in density, up to 10 vol% LATP, is observed, which is partially caused by the addition of LATP. The salt concentration, in the whole electrolyte, is practically constant. Considering the dilution effect caused by the presence of LATP, this indicates that the density of the polymer phase is slightly increasing with LATP. On the contrary, the sample HSE-20 has similar density as HSE-10, although having double LATP concentration. This means that the density in the polymer phase is lower than in HSE-10, as LATP has a higher density than the polymer phase. This suggests a more disordered morphology and possibly the presence of residual porosity in the polymer phase. Consequently, the overall salt concentration in HSE-20 is slightly lower than in the other samples.

The morphology of the four HSEs was analyzed by cross-section scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The SEM images (**Figure 1a–e**) show that the membranes have thickness of ≈ 100 μm , and that the micrometer-sized LATP particles are homogeneously dispersed throughout the thickness of the membranes. The latter show significant roughness at high LATP concentrations (HSE-10, HSE-20), with some of the LATP particles exposed on the surface. Higher magnification images of HSE-20 (**Figure 1f**) show that, even at the highest LATP concentration, there is hardly direct contact between LATP particles, indicating that there is no Li⁺ percolation pathway across the inorganic phase.

The thermal behavior of the four HSE membranes was studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The TGA profiles of the main electrolyte components (LiTFSI, LATP, PEGDME, and p(EO-PO), **Figure 2a**) indicate that the thermal stability is limited by the PEGDME, which starts decomposing at ≈ 200 °C. The copolymer starts decomposing at slightly higher temperatures, whereas LiTFSI is stable up to 300 °C. As expected, no significant mass loss is observed for LATP in the explored temperature range. Correspondently, the HSEs show decomposition onset at ≈ 200 °C (**Figure 2b**), with main decomposition at ≈ 300 °C. The two LATP-rich samples (HSE-10, HSE-20) show slightly higher thermal stability, with a smoother mass loss at low temperatures. In part, this is due to the lower amount of polymer phase in these electrolytes, but it may also indicate that LATP retards the decomposition of the organic components at low temperatures. However, the analysis of the differential TGA profiles (**Figure 2c**) shows a progressively decreasing onset of the main decomposition event, from ≈ 320 °C in HSE-00 to ≈ 270 °C in HSE-20. Overall TGA indicates that LATP enhances thermal stability below 250 °C, while accelerating violent decomposition at higher temperatures.

Beside the thermal stability, the study of the calorimetric profiles of polymer electrolytes is important to understand their transport properties, as the ionic conductivity is affected by the glass transition temperature (T_g) and by the polymer morphology. For instance, the ionic conductivity of amorphous polymer electrolytes is related to the T_g through the Vogel–Tamman–Fulcher (VTF) equation^[48]

$$\sigma = AT^{-0.5}e^{-B/(T-T_0)} \quad (1)$$

where A and B are empirical parameters and T_0 is the ideal glass transition temperature, which is equal to $T_0 \approx T_g - 40$. The $\ln(\sigma)$ versus $1/T$ profiles of amorphous polymer electrolytes are characterized by a characteristic curvature which is determined by this formula. In addition, semicrystalline polymer electrolytes are characterized by a lower ionic conductivity with respect to amorphous polymer electrolytes. A melting temperature (T_m) can be observed as a discontinuity in the conductivity profiles, and the ionic conductivity in the semicrystalline region follows an Arrhenius dependence on temperature. For this reason, differential scanning calorimetry was carried out to detect whether addition of LATP has any influence on the thermal behavior of the HSEs. The DSC traces of the four HSEs (**Figure 1e**) show a second order thermal transition at ≈ -50 °C, assigned to the glass transition of the polymer matrix, and two first-order transitions at ≈ -7 and 25 °C, assigned to the melting of PEGDME and polyether, respectively. The thermal properties of the HSEs are hardly affected by the addition of LATP. The T_g and T_m are approximately constant (**Table 2**). On the contrary, the melting enthalpy progressively decreases with increasing concentration of LATP, but this is just the result of the decreasing fraction of polymer in the HSEs. After normalization on the polymer fraction, the melting enthalpy is approximately constant indicating the lack of amorphization derived from the addition of the inorganic filler. Moreover, the segmental mobility of the polymer matrix, which is related to the T_g , is not affected by the presence of the LATP. For comparison, the DSC profile of the pure copolymer shows a T_g at -56 °C, T_m at 49 °C, and enthalpy of 81 J g⁻¹ (**Figure S1a**, Supporting

Figure 1. Cross-section SEM images of a) HSE-00, b) HSE-05, c) HSE-10, and d) HSE-20, taken at a magnification of 800x; e) HSE-20, at magnification of 800x (secondary electron detector); f) HSE-20, at magnification of 2000x.

Figure 2. Thermal properties of HSEs. a) TGA profiles of the main HSE components; b) TGA profiles of the four HSEs; c) differential TGA profiles of the four HSEs; d) DSC profiles of the four HSEs.

Table 2. Thermal properties of HSEs with different concentrations of LATP: glass transition temperature, melting temperature, melting enthalpy and melting enthalpy normalized on the polymer content.

	T_g [°C]	$T_m,2$ [°C]	ΔH [J g ⁻¹]	ΔH (norm) [J g ⁻¹]
HSE-00	-53	25	30.3	56
HSE-05	-54	26	36.8	77
HSE-10	-53	24	23.1	55
HSE-20	-52	26	19.5	59

Information). Thus, the HSEs have higher T_g , lower T_m , and lower crystallinity than the pure copolymer, which is attributed to the combined effects of the salt (coordination of Li⁺ has a stiffening effect on the polyether chains, increasing the T_g), crosslinking, and plasticizer. Pristine PEGDME, on the other hand, has T_m at 16 °C (Figure S1b, Supporting Information). Overall, DSC results suggest that there is little interaction between the LATP particles and the polymer matrix; thus, the DSC analysis predicts a single VTF-like behavior of the ionic conductivity at temperatures higher than 25 °C. Furthermore, the ionic conductivity within the polymer phase, which is limited by the segmental mobility of the polymer matrix, should be comparable in all electrolytes.

The mechanical properties of the four HSEs were characterized by tensile test (Figure S2, Supporting Information and Table 3). The addition of LATP enhances the mechanical properties of the materials. This can be readily observed, qualitatively, by handling the membranes, and is confirmed by the increase of the Young modulus and toughness (Table 3). The improvement is particularly evident between HSE-00 and HSE-05, also because HSE-00 shows a clear yielding point at very low yield stress (0.2 MPa), while LATP-containing membranes show a smoother transition between the elastic and plastic regimes. Data at higher LATP loading are affected by large scattering, but average values of modulus and toughness consistently increase up to HSE-20. This result is particularly important for the application in lithium metal batteries, as the growth of lithium dendrites is affected by the electrolyte modulus.^[49] In addition, processability is favored by higher membranes stiffness, especially considering the need of using very thin polymer electrolyte layers in batteries. On the other hand, a higher modulus is usually accompanied by a lower ionic conductivity.^[50] Thus, a decrease of the ionic conductivity with increasing LATP content is foreseen, on the base of the mechanical test results.

Table 3. Mechanical properties of the four HSEs, measured by tensile test. Young modulus (E), stress at break (σ_b), elongation at break (ϵ_b), and tensile toughness (T).

	E [MPa]	σ_b [MPa]	ϵ_b	T [MPa]
HSE-00	0.21 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.03	4.9 ± 0.7	1.5 ± 0.1
HSE-05	0.24 ± 0.05	0.59 ± 0.03	4.1 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.3
HSE-10	0.3 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.4	8 ± 3	6 ± 3
HSE-20	0.4 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.3	8 ± 3	8 ± 4

2.1. Ionic Conductivity and Interface Resistance

The ionic conductivity of the four HSEs was measured by impedance spectroscopy in the frequency range from 32 MHz to 1 Hz, and in the temperature range between 25 and 70 °C. Inductive contributions dominate the spectra at very high frequencies, and for this reason the analysis was conducted on a more restricted frequency range (up to ≈1 MHz). The Nyquist plot of the LATP-free electrolyte (Figure S3a, Supporting Information) showed a high frequency semicircle followed, at low frequencies, by a capacitive tail. These spectra can be modeled by a simple equivalent circuit, consisting of an RC circuit followed by a constant-phase element (CPE). The only resistance in the circuit corresponds to the electrolyte ionic resistance, and the low-frequency CPE to capacitive contribution due to ions accumulation at the blocking electrodes. The impedance spectra of LATP-containing electrolytes (Figure S3b–d, Supporting Information) show additional features, which are better visualized in Nyquist plots of the admittance (Figure 3). In these plots, an additional semicircle is visible at high frequencies (the frequency increases from the left to the right), whose size increases with the LATP concentration. The impedance/admittance spectra can be modeled with the ladder equivalent circuit depicted in Figure S4 (Supporting Information), comprising two resistances (R_1 , R_2). The first resistance (R_1) corresponds to the high-frequency intercept of the complex admittance/impedance plots ($Y_{loc} = 1/R_1$), whereas the second resistance (R_2) corresponds to the difference between the low and high-frequency intercepts in the impedance plots and is equal to: $R_2 = 1/Y_{tot} - 1/Y_{loc}$ in the admittance plots. This equivalent circuit was selected on the base of an empirical, qualitative analysis of the EIS spectra. Nonetheless, additional features in the EIS spectra of LATP-containing HSEs were somehow expected. Indeed, multiphase heterogeneous materials usually show additional polarizations phenomena, owing to the accumulation of ions at the internal interfaces.^[51] With regard to the choice of the specific equivalent circuit, a ladder circuit provides the same response as the typical Voigt circuit with the same number of elements, but the impedance resulting from a Voigt circuit is invariant upon permuting two consecutive RC circuits, whereas this is not the case for the ladder circuit.^[52] For this reason, the latter was used for the analysis of the impedance spectra.

From the impedance/admittance spectra, two values of conductivity can be obtained. Firstly, a high-frequency conductivity, σ_{loc} , calculated from R_1 alone

$$\sigma_{loc} = Y_{loc} \frac{L}{A} = \frac{1}{R_1} \frac{L}{A} \quad (2)$$

And, second, a low-frequency conductivity, σ_{tot} , calculated from the sum of R_1 and R_2 :

$$\sigma_{tot} = Y_{tot} \frac{L}{A} = \frac{1}{(R_1 + R_2)} \frac{L}{A} \quad (3)$$

The profiles of σ_{loc} versus the inverse of the temperature are depicted in Figure 4a. In HSE-00, $\sigma_{loc} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ S cm⁻¹ at 25 °C. From HSE-00 to HSE-10, σ_{loc} is practically constant. On the contrary, a slight decrease is observed from HSE-10 to HSE-20, for which $\sigma_{loc} = 6.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ S cm⁻¹ at 25 °C. The close values of σ_{loc} indicate that the latter is strongly influenced by the conductivity of

Figure 3. Nyquist admittance plots at 50 °C of the four HSEs: a) HSE-00; b) HSE-05; c) HSE-10; d) HSE-20. The frequency increases from the left to the right.

the polymer phase. The lower value of σ_{loc} in HSE-20 is attributed to the lower density of the polymer phase (see Table 1). The relation with the conductivity of the polymer phase is also confirmed by the dependence of σ_{loc} with the temperature, which resembles the VTF behavior (Equation (1)) typical of polymer electrolytes. No discontinuities are observed in the conductivity profiles, indicating that the electrolytes are amorphous in the whole examined temperature range. This agrees with the DSC results, which predict a single VTF behavior above 25 °C.

Specifically, the high-frequency conductivity, σ_{loc} is attributed to the local ionic conductivity in the electrolyte, at timescales short enough ($t \ll 10^{-5}$ s) that no ions accumulation and no Li^+ transfer occur at the LATP/polymer interface. σ_{loc} is equal to the effective conductivity of the HSEs, which is given by the Maxwell-Garnett mixing rule^[53]

$$\sigma_{loc} = \sigma_{PE} \left[1 + \frac{3(\sigma_{LATP} - \sigma_{PE})f_{LATP}}{\sigma_{LATP} + 2\sigma_{PE} - (\sigma_{LATP} - \sigma_{PE})f_{LATP}} \right] \quad (4)$$

where σ_{LATP} and σ_{PE} are the conductivities of the ceramic and polymer phases, respectively, and f_{LATP} is the volume fraction of LATP. Considering that an amorphous polymer matrix is used,

the presence of a third additional phase, at the interface between the two main phases, is excluded.

In order to calculate the conductivity of the polymer phase in the electrolytes, the conductivity of LATP was first calculated in HSE-05, by assuming that the molar conductivity was constant in HSE-00 and HSE-05. The polymer phase conductivity in HSE-05 was thus assumed to be equal to

$$\sigma_{PE,05} = \sigma_{PE,00} \frac{C_{LiTFSI,05}}{C_{LiTFSI,00} (1 - f_{LATP,05})} \quad (5)$$

where $C_{LiTFSI,i}$ is the LiTFSI concentration in the electrolyte (reported in Table 1) and $f_{LATP,05}$ is the molar fraction of LATP in HSE-05 (also reported in Table 1). The resulting conductivity was then used to calculate the conductivity of LATP, σ_{LATP} , with equation (4) (Figure 4a). $\sigma_{PE,05}$ is practically equal to $\sigma_{loc,05}$, which is expected owing to the high concentration of the polymer phase. σ_{LATP} is $7.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ S cm^{-1} at room temperature, that is slightly lower than $\sigma_{PE,05}$. This value is significantly lower than the reported grain-core conductivity of LATP (≈ 2 mS cm^{-1} at room temperature or even higher, as reported by Samsinger et al.).^[54] Ionic conductivity measurements performed on LATP pellets sandwiched between PE membranes (results not shown) indicate

Figure 4. Ionic conductivity and interface resistance of the four HSEs between 25 and 70 °C. a) Local ionic conductivity versus the inverse of the temperature. The points represent the experimental data, whereas the dotted lines and the orange dashed line are the ionic conductivity of the polymer electrolyte phase and of LATP, respectively, calculated with Equation (4); b) total ionic conductivity versus the inverse of the temperature. The points represent the experimental data, and the dashed lines are the effective conductivity calculated with Equation (6); c) ratio of total versus local conductivity $\rho = \sigma_{tot} / \sigma_{loc}$. The lines are a guide for the eye; d) $R2$ versus inverse of the temperature. Points represent the experimental data, the dotted lines the values of $R2_{MG}$, calculated with Equation (7), and the full lines the fitting with Arrhenius equation.

a grain-core conductivity of 1.5 mS cm^{-1} and a total pellet conductivity of $8 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at room temperature. This is attributed to high grain-boundary resistances, due to a chemical composition of the glass-ceramic material not being optimized for sintering applications, in contrast to the one used in the cited study.^[54] The calculated σ_{LATP} increases more rapidly with the temperature than $\sigma_{PE,05}$, so that already at 50 °C $\sigma_{LATP} > \sigma_{PE,05}$. Arrhenius fitting of σ_{LATP} gives an activation energy of 0.6 eV. The conductivity of the inorganic phase was assumed to be constant with the LATP concentration, and its value was used to calculate the conductivity of the polymer phase in HSE-10 and HSE-20 (Figure 4a). In HSE-10, $\sigma_{PE,10}$ is still quite close to $\sigma_{loc,10}$; however, in HSE-20 a significant decrease of $\sigma_{PE,20}$ is obtained, possibly indicating that the high concentrations of LATP negatively affects the ionic conductivity of the polymer phase. Altogether, the results are in agreement with the observation by Trevisanello and co-workers, where LATP has no positive effect on the ionic conductivity of amorphous HSEs.^[18]

The low-frequency conductivity, σ_{tot} (Figure 4b), is attributed to the long-range conductivity, which is the relevant parameter for assessing the overall electrochemical performance of the electrolytes. In HSE-00, σ_{tot} is obviously equal to $\sigma_{loc} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 25 °C. The total conductivity decreases slightly from HSE-00 to HSE-10, with $\sigma_{tot,10} = 7.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at

25 °C (Figure 4c). From HSE-10 to HSE-20, a steeper decrease is observed, with $\sigma_{tot,20} = 4.0 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 25 °C. It is noteworthy that $R2$ decreases faster than $R1$ with increasing temperatures, so that at high temperatures (for $T > 60$ °C) $\sigma_{loc} \approx \sigma_{tot}$. This additional polarization is attributed to the high interface resistance for the Li^+ transfer between LATP particles and the polymer phase. A high interface resistance decreases the effective conductivity of the LATP particles σ_{LATP}^{eff} . For very high values of interface resistance, $\sigma_{LATP}^{eff} \approx 0$, and LATP particles behave as insulating particles dispersed in a conductive medium. On the contrary, negligible values of $R2$ indicate that unhindered Li^+ transfer takes place. This condition is achieved only at high temperatures. The participation of LATP particles in the Li^+ transport process can be thus estimated by calculating the effective conductivity σ_{eff} with the Maxwell-Garnett mixing rule (Equation (4)), with the previously calculated values of $\sigma_{PE,i}$ and by imposing $\sigma_{LATP}^{eff} = 0$. The resulting formula is as follows

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_{PE} \left[1 - \frac{3f_{LATP}}{2 + f_{LATP}} \right] \quad (6)$$

The resulting values of σ_{eff} were finally compared with the experimental values of σ_{tot} (Figure 4b).

Figure 5. a) Interface capacitance, divided by the electrodes area. Empty dots are multiplied for the volume fraction of LATP; b) time constants τ_1 (full dots) and τ_2 (empty dots), calculated by multiplying C_{int} for R1 and R2, respectively.

For HSE-05, σ_{eff} is largely superimposed to σ_{tot} , indicating negligible LATP contribution in the whole temperature range. With HSE-10, σ_{eff} is close to σ_{tot} at low temperatures, but σ_{tot} increases faster than σ_{eff} with the temperature, indicating increasing LATP contribution at high temperatures to the long-range conductivity. In HSE-20, σ_{eff} is lower than σ_{tot} in the whole temperature range, and the spread between the two values increases with temperature. The lower value of σ_{eff} , with respect to σ_{tot} , is possibly caused by an underestimation of $\sigma_{PE,20}$, but the increasing spread is clearly caused by the decrease of the interface resistance. Altogether, the analysis reveals that LATP contribution to the conductivity increases with the temperature, and that this effect becomes more intense with increasing LATP content. This can be easily observed by comparing the conductivity ratio $\rho = \sigma_{tot}/\sigma_{loc}$ (Figure 4c). The conductivity ratio is practically constant in HSE-05 at $\rho \approx 0.9$, but it increases with the temperature in both HSE-10 and HSE-20. The increase is also more evident in HSE-20, for which ρ increases from 0.6 at 25 °C to 0.8 at 70 °C.

Further details on the interface resistance can be obtained through the analysis of R2, and of the parallel capacitance (C_{int}). As noted above, R2 increases with LATP concentration (Figure 4c). More specifically, R2 is roughly proportional to the volume fraction of LATP (Figure 4d). The dependence of R2 with the temperature is of Arrhenius type, and the activation energy is ≈ 0.55 eV, constant with LATP concentration, thus very close to the activation energy of the inorganic phase. R2 can be estimated by combining Equations (4) and (6). The resulting formula is as follows

$$R_{2MG} = \frac{9\sigma_{LATP}f_{LATP}}{2\sigma_{PE}(1-f_{LATP})} \frac{1}{\sigma_{LATP} + 2\sigma_{PE} + 2(\sigma_{LATP} - \sigma_{PE})f_{LATP}} \frac{L}{A} \quad (7)$$

The values of R_{2MG} , calculated through Equation (7), are also shown in Figure 4d. The calculated values are roughly close to the experimental ones (except for HSE-20, for which $\sigma_{LATP}^{eff} > 0$), but the Maxwell equation predicts a VTF dependence of R2 on the temperature, whereas the experimental dependence, as noted previously, is clearly of Arrhenius type, with activation energy of ≈ 0.55 eV, constant with LATP concentration. The area-specific resistance R_{2sp} calculated by normalizing R2 on the LATP volume fraction and multiplying for the electrodes area, ranges from 270 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ in HSE-05 to 450 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ in HSE-20, at 25 °C (Figure S5,

Supporting Information). At 60 °C, R_{2sp} varies between 20 and 30 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$. Although R_{2sp} is only indirectly related to the interface resistance between the LATP particles and the polymer matrix, it is quite interesting that the values of R_{2sp} are close to the values of interface resistance previously reported for NASICON-based multilayered model systems.^[18,43,55]

The interface capacitance, C_{int} , was calculated from the values of CPE2, R1, and R2 (see Figure S4 in the Supporting Information), with the following equation^[56]

$$C_{int} = \left(\frac{1}{R1} + \frac{1}{R2} \right)^{\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\alpha} \right)} Q2^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (8)$$

where Q2 and α are the pseudocapacitance and exponent of the CPE2 element in Figure S4 (Supporting Information), respectively. The values of C_{int} divided by the electrodes area, are reported in Figure 5a. In all samples, C_{int} is below 1 $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$, confirming that this capacitance is related to an internal interface and not to an electrodes interface. Furthermore, C_{int} decreases with the LATP concentration, thus further confirming that it is related to the LATP interface. Indeed, by dividing C_{int} for the LATP volume fraction, the values of C_{int} fall into a single master curve (Figure 5a), resembling the behavior of R2. Interestingly, C_{int} increases with temperature at $T > 40$ °C. This may be related to the decreasing interface resistance.

By multiplying C_{int} for R1 and R2, two time constants can be obtained, namely τ_1 and τ_2 , respectively. The first one is the characteristic charging time of the double layer at the LATP interface, whereas the origin of τ_2 is more ambiguous, although it is possibly related to the conductivity of LATP and to the interface resistance. The values of τ_1 and τ_2 are shown in Figure 5b. τ_1 varies between 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} s, and it decreases with increasing LATP concentration, owing to the decreasing values of C_{int} . τ_1 decreases initially with increasing temperature, but it is approximately constant at $T > 40$ °C. This behavior, which is related to the increasing values of C_{int} , is possibly caused by the decrease of the interface resistance and by the increasing rate of Li^+ transfer across the interface. On the contrary, τ_2 is practically constant and generally lower than τ_1 , varying from $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s at room temperature to $\approx 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ s at 70 °C. The constant values of τ_2 suggest that R2 is strongly correlated with C_{int} .

Figure 6. Self-diffusion coefficients and transference numbers by PFG-NMR: diffusion coefficients of a) ^7Li and b) ^{19}F from 20 to 80 °C; c) comparison of the diffusion coefficients at 60 °C; d) ionic conductivity calculated from the diffusion coefficients with the Nernst–Einstein equation; e) Haven ratios between 30 and 70 °C; f) lithium transference numbers, calculated from the diffusion coefficients of ^7Li and ^{19}F , between 20 and 70 °C. The red asterisk indicates the transference number calculated by potentiostatic polarization method.

2.2. Solid-State NMR Characterization

Information on the individual mobility of anions and cations was obtained by PFG-NMR. The self-diffusion coefficients of ^7Li (D_{Li}) and ^{19}F (D_F) between 20 and 80 °C are depicted in **Figure 6a,b**, respectively. Both diffusion coefficients increase with temperature between 10^{-12} to 10^{-11} $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, but the values of D_F are generally higher than those of D_{Li} , as could be expected for polymer electrolytes, since ethylene oxide units strongly coordinate with Li^+ cations. The activation energies of the diffusion coefficients were determined by fitting with the Arrhenius equation. The activation energy is ≈ 0.3 eV for D_{Li} , practically constant with LAMP, and in the case of D_F is comprised between 0.4 and 0.3 eV, decreasing with LAMP concentration.

Interestingly, D_F decreases with LAMP concentration, especially at high temperature (**Figure 6c**), indicating that the mobility of TFSI^- anions is negatively affected by the presence of LAMP. On the contrary, D_{Li} is almost constant, suggesting that the diffusivity of Li^+ cations in the LAMP particles is close to the diffu-

sivity in the polymer matrix. It must be noted that the fitting of the ^7Li signals, to retrieve the diffusion coefficients, was carried out with a single exponential function. For comparison, the fitting was additionally performed with two exponentials, which resulted in quite similar diffusion coefficients. However, since the quality of the fitting was only marginally improved by fitting with a two-exponential function, fitting with one exponential was ultimately preferred. The difficulty in differentiating the diffusion coefficients of the two phases is also related to the timescale of the PFG-NMR experiment. The diffusion delay of 25 ms is significantly larger than the characteristic time for ions accumulation at the LAMP surface which, as observed by EIS, is in the order of 10^{-6} s. The diffusion length, given a diffusion coefficient of $5 \cdot 10^{-12}$ $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ at 60 °C, is slightly lower than 1 μm . This is larger than the average particles radius (≈ 0.7 μm), thus sufficient for most Li^+ within the LAMP particles to experience the particles boundary. Although this is not necessarily related to the characteristic time of the Li^+ exchange across the interface, the results of EIS experiments suggest that a timescale of 25 ms is sufficient to give

a picture of the long-range transport properties of the HSEs. To confirm this assumption, PFG-NMR experiments were repeated at longer diffusion delay of 200 ms, on the samples HSE-00 and HSE-20. The resulting diffusion coefficients (Figure S6, Supporting Information) are close to those measured at 25 ms, except the fluorine diffusion coefficient of fluorine in HSE-20, which is slightly higher than the one measured at 25 ms. In the following analysis, for sake of coherence, the values obtained at 25 ms will be used. The diffusion coefficients of ^7Li , as determined by PFG-NMR, should be understood as the long-range diffusivity in the HSEs, accounting also for the contribution of the interface resistance. Consequently, the results of the PFG-NMR experiment can be compared with the long-range ionic conductivity, by applying the Nernst-Einstein equation. This allows determining whether there are any ion pairing effects caused by the filler. To calculate the ionic conductivity from the diffusion coefficients, the concentration of charge carriers is needed. The effective charge carrier concentration is not known, but two limiting scenarios can be conceived. In the first case, the total ions concentration is used, including also the Li^+ in the LAMP particles.^[53] In the second case, only the salt concentration is considered. In the former case, the Nernst-Einstein equation assumes the following form^[57]

$$\sigma_{\text{NMR}} = \frac{e^2}{k_B T} (C_{\text{Li}} D_{\text{Li}} + C_{\text{F}} D_{\text{F}}) \quad (9)$$

With e being the elementary charge, k_B the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, and C_{Li} and C_{F} the concentrations of Li^+ and TFSI $^-$, respectively. The values of σ_{NMR} , for HSE-00, are close to the experimental values of σ_{tot} (compare Figure 4b and Figure 6d), with a Haven ratio H_R (that is, the ratio between σ_{NMR} and σ_{tot}) ranging between 1.2 and 1.3 (Figure 6e). On the contrary, the conductivity of the LAMP-containing samples is overestimated, approaching σ_{NMR} of HSE-00 and thus close to the values of σ_{tot} . This is expected as the concentration of cations C_{Li} in Equation (9) considers also the Li^+ in the inorganic phase, which at low temperatures is essentially confined owing to the high interface resistance. Nonetheless, the Haven ratio decreases with the temperature (Figure 6e), thus confirming that Li^+ plays increasingly a role in the conduction process. For comparison, we can calculate again the conductivity, by considering only the salt concentration. This is done by substituting C_{Li} and C_{F} with C_{salt} in Equation (9). In this case, $\sigma_{\text{NMR}} \approx \sigma_{\text{tot}}$ also for the LAMP-containing samples, and the Haven ratio is close to 1 in all samples (Figure S7, Supporting Information). If the values of HSE-00 are taken as a reference, lower values of H_R are observed, in LAMP-containing samples, only at $T \geq 60$ °C. In this case, we can assume that the concentration of Li^+ is possibly underestimated. Despite this, the use of the salt concentration alone, in the Nernst-Einstein equation, gives a good approximation for the calculation of the total conductivity. The Nernst-Einstein equation can also be applied reversely to calculate the salt diffusion coefficient from the ionic conductivity. This can be compared with the average salt diffusion coefficient by PFG-NMR. Again, there is a good agreement between the results of PFG-NMR and of the conductivity measurements, with diffusivity values ranging between $4 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $8 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and decreasing between HSE-00 and HSE-20 (Figure S8, Supporting Information). The values are close to those obtained by interrupted current method

($5\text{--}6 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 60 °C), although in this case no effect of LAMP is observed.

Altogether, it appears that, at least at high temperatures, the observed decrease of ionic conductivity is caused by a decrease of the anions' diffusivity. This is attributed to the anions-specific blocking effect exercised by the LAMP particles. On the contrary, Li^+ diffusion is unhindered by LAMP particles, at least at high temperatures. The larger Haven ratio at low temperatures is attributed to the high interface resistance blocking the transfer of Li^+ . Overall, this results in a slight increase of the Li^+ transference number at high temperatures: The latter was calculated from the diffusivity values^[58]

$$t^+ = \frac{D_{\text{Li}}}{D_{\text{Li}} + D_{\text{F}}} \quad (10)$$

It must be noted that the transference number calculated in this way assumes an equal concentration of cations and anions, and thus is possibly underestimated, as the Li^+ concentration in the LAMP particles is not considered. However, as noted above, the use of the salt concentration is a good approximation when considering the long-range charge transport. At room temperature, the four HSEs have similar transference numbers of 0.38 (Figure 6f). However, the values start to diverge at ≈ 50 °C. At 60 °C, the sample HSE-20 has transference number of over 0.41, whereas HSE-00 has transference number slightly below 0.3. It must be noted that this difference is quite low. Indeed, transference number T^+ , determined by potentiostatic polarization method, is equal to $T^+ = 0.35$ in all samples (chronoamperometric profiles and impedance spectra are shown in Figure S9 in the Supporting Information). The value is close to the one determined by PFG-NMR, but no effect is observed due to LAMP. Altogether, the experimental results do not confirm a significant increase of the transference number due to LAMP. On the other hand, the close values obtained by potentiostatic polarization method and PFG-NMR suggest the absence of ion pairing effects. This is confirmed by solid-state NMR measurements (see later discussion in this section) and is expected owing to the high dissociation degree of LiTFSI.^[59]

Finally, the lithium transference numbers, obtained by PFG-NMR, were combined with the total ionic conductivity, to calculate the cationic conductivity σ_{Li^+} (Figure 7). Owing to the increase of the transference number, the cationic conductivity remains constant up to 10% LAMP. At 60 °C, the cationic conductivity is $\approx 1.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, up to 10% LAMP. At 20% LAMP, a slight decrease is observed, with $\sigma_{\text{Li}^+} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. To summarize, at moderate LAMP content, since the decrease of the ionic conductivity is mostly caused by the blocking of anions, it has almost no effect on the cationic conductivity. This suggests that the electrochemical performances should not be compromised by the decrease of the total conductivity, at least at moderate contents of LAMP. This, combined with the results of the mechanical measurements, suggests that the overall cycling performance should be enhanced by the addition of moderate amounts of LAMP.

Electrochemical characterization suggests that, at 60 °C, LAMP particles participate in the long-range Li^+ transport process. To assess this hypothesis, a ^6Li - ^7Li isotope exchange experiment was carried out. This type of experiment, which combines electrochemical ^6Li - ^7Li isotope exchange with NMR, has been used for

Figure 7. a) Li⁺ ionic conductivity as a function of temperature, and b) at 60 °C, compared to the total ionic conductivity.

probing the participation of active fillers in the conduction process of HSEs.^[14,40,41] Isotope substitution of ⁷Li by ⁶Li in a HSE-10 electrolyte was forced by cycling galvanostatically the electrolyte between 99% enriched ⁶Li metal electrodes, as described in the Experimental Section. The possible ⁷Li-⁶Li exchange in LAMP and the polymer matrix was subsequently assessed by ⁷Li and ⁶Li 1D NMR measurements, performed ex situ on the recovered electrolyte. From this experiment, the Li-ions stemming from the LAMP particles and from the Lithium salt can be distinguished from the Li-ions coming from the metal foil by solid-state NMR, by recording samples of HSE-10 before and after plating versus ⁶Li metal.

⁷Li and ⁶Li NMR spectra were collected on the pristine HSE-10 membrane, as a reference (Figure 8a,b, respectively). The ⁷Li spectrum of HSE-10 before plating (HSE-10-Pristine in Figure 8a) shows two highly overlapped signals at around -1.3 and -1.1 ppm. From the deconvolution of the ⁷Li spectra of HSE-10 and its comparison with the one of HSE-00 (Figure S10, Supporting Information), these two signals can be assigned to the Li⁺ ions in the polymer matrix and the LAMP, respectively.

The comparison of the NMR spectra before and after plating, Figure 8a, clearly shows that, after the ⁶Li plating, the intensity of the ⁷Li signal of the HSE-10 sample did almost disappear. The signal reduction clearly involves Li NMR signals from both the LAMP and the polymer phases. Parallely, the ⁶Li signal increases drastically, giving an intense asymmetric peak, as expected after homogeneous ⁷Li to ⁶Li exchange in both the polymer and LAMP phases. This result clearly demonstrates that Li⁺ ions at the polymer and LAMP phases must be interchanging. The spectra shown in Figure 8b also shows that the ⁶Li NMR signal linewidth increases after the plating. This phenomenon, which could be attributed to the increased heterogeneity of the membrane,^[44] makes the deconvolution complicated. However, since the alteration of ⁷Li signal intensities is homogeneous, it can be concluded that the Li⁺ ions in both the polymer and ceramic phases are mobile and are accessible for ion transport. This suggests the occurrence of Li⁺ ion exchange between the polymer matrix and the LAMP particles. The results also show that this exchange is not limited to the Li atoms on the surface of LAMP, but rather all the Li atoms in the bulk of LAMP can be substituted by the ones from the metal foil.

⁶Li EXSY experiments have been carried out with the pristine HSE-20 sample to unequivocally demonstrate ion exchange in the ceramic-polymer interface, the same way as in our previous works regarding LLZO-PEO electrolytes.^[14,47] In these spectra, the diagonal peaks (identical chemical shifts in both dimensions) correspond to regular signals of the identified components of the sample, while the off-diagonal responses (cross-peaks) represent magnetization transfer between the components either via chemical exchange or through dipolar interaction between neighboring spins separated in space by less than 5 Å. Taking into account that natural abundance of ⁶Li is less than 8%, the probability of observing several ⁶Li isotopes at a close distance from each other is negligible. Moreover, the low dipolar moment of ⁶Li would make spin diffusion through dipolar interactions even more unlikely. It means that the appearance of cross-peaks in our spectra clearly demonstrates the presence of dynamic physical exchange processes of Li⁺ ions between the two phases in the HSE. Intensity of cross-peaks depends on a mixing time – time delay in the EXSY experiment, during which magnetization transfer occurs (Figure 8c and Figure S11, Supporting Information). By running the experiment multiple times with different mixing time, one can quantify the exchange rate. In the analyzed sample at 20 °C, the time constant of the exchange is about 300 ms, with the plateau observed at around 1 s, while at 60 °C the constant decreases to 50 ms and the plateau is reached at 400 ms (Figure 8d).

Beside probing the participation of the LAMP particles in the long-range charge transport, solid-state NMR can be used also to investigate the local ions dynamics, which may be affected by chemical interactions between the ions and polymer matrix and the filler particles. For instance, possible chemical interactions of the anions with the particles surface may give rise to a decrease of the anion's mobility, prompting an increase of the cation transference number and of the oxidative stability in HSEs.^[29] To study the possible TFSI⁻ aggregation at the LAMP surface, ¹⁹F NMR experiments were conducted and T₁ relaxation times were investigated. The longitudinal relaxation times of the nuclear magnetizations in NMR depend strongly on the local mobilities and time fluctuations of the chemical environments. In this line, the attachment of anions to the surface of a filler would result in different anion environments with distinct relaxation times and line shapes.^[60] Since in the ¹⁹F 1D spectra of all samples (HSE-00, HSE-10, and HSE-20) only single lines were observed,

Figure 8. Solid-state NMR characterization of LAMP-based HSEs. a) ^7Li NMR spectra of HSE-10, pristine (black line) and after electrochemically driven isotope exchange (red line); b) ^6Li NMR spectra of HSE-10, pristine (black line) and after isotope exchange (red line); c) ^6Li 2D EXSY spectra of HSE-20 at 60 °C, at mixing times of 10 ms (red contour) and 600 ms (blue contour); d) normalized intensity of the off-diagonal peaks in the ^6Li 2D EXSY spectra of HSE-20 at 20 and 60 °C, as a function of the mixing time; e) ^{19}F NMR saturation recovery experiments of HSEs with different LAMP concentrations. Fitting line was obtained considering a single exponential; f) ^{19}F linewidth at variable temperature, with and without LAMP.

complementary T_1 saturation-recovery experiments were conducted to examine the possible overlapping of resonances. As shown in Figure 8e, the data could be perfectly fitted in all cases with a single exponential term, and similar ^{19}F relaxation times ($T_1 = 0.76$ s) were obtained, indicating no anion immobilization upon the addition of LAMP. If this were the case, different ^{19}F NMR resonances and/or multiexponential behavior in T_1 would be expected.

To compare the anion dynamics in the HSE-00 and HSE-10 in more detail, variable temperature NMR experiments were performed and the linewidths (FWHM) as a function of temperature were plotted in Figure 8f. The motional narrowing curve shows similar behavior of the ^{19}F signals of the TFSI^- anions between these two hybrid electrolyte membranes. For both HSE-00 and HSE-10, the motional narrowing is completed at around 20 °C, and the linewidth of the rigid lattice is at least 32 kHz,

which would result in jump rates ($1/\tau_{\text{NMR}}$) above $2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the temperature of inflection point (-31 °C). A similar experiment to follow ^7Li local dynamics by NMR was not feasible due to the overlapping between ^7Li signals from the polymer and LAMP phases. The results agree with the T_1 relaxation time measurements, and further prove that filler incorporation keeps the anion local dynamics rather unaffected. It must be noted that this result is not in conflict with the previous results of impedance spectroscopy and PFG-NMR experiments. Indeed, impedance spectroscopy showed that the local molar conductivity is not affected by the introduction of LAMP, which agrees well with the results of the NMR linewidth experiments. On the other hand, as noted above, the diffusion coefficients determined by PFG-NMR are related to the long-range transport, and thus are partially decoupled from the local mobility, owing to the presence of the high interface resistance.

Figure 9. Plating/stripping profiles of the four HSEs, at 60 °C. Tests were performed at fixed capacity (1 mAh cm⁻²) and increasing current density. The current density is indicated as C-rate, where 1C (or C/1) is 1 mA cm⁻². The red asterisk indicates the minimum C-rate at which voltage instability or short circuit is observed. a) HSE-00; b) HSE-05; c) HSE-10; d) HSE-20.

2.3. Plating/Stripping Test

Plating/stripping tests were carried out to test the resistance of the four electrolytes against dendrites growth, and thus to verify the combined effect of LAMP on the mechanical and transport properties of the electrolytes. The tests were performed at 60 °C, with fixed capacity of 1 mAh cm⁻² and at increasing current density, to determine the maximum current density at which stable plating/stripping can be achieved. Thus, this test gives an indication of the limiting current density at which the hybrid electrolytes can be cycled. The plating/stripping profiles are shown in **Figure 9**. HSE-00 shows stable cycling only up to 0.1 mA cm⁻² (C/10), whereas voltage instabilities (soft shorts) and a clear short circuit are observed at 0.2 mA cm⁻² (C/5) and 0.33 mA cm⁻² (C/3), respectively. HSE-05 and HSE-10 show better plating/stripping performance, with stable cycling at 0.2 mA cm⁻² (C/5) and voltage instabilities starting from 0.33 mA cm⁻² (C/3). In both cases, no clear short circuit is observed. HSE-20, on the contrary, shows a short circuit already at 0.2 mA cm⁻² (C/5).

The enhanced plating/stripping performance obtained with HSE-05 and HSE-10 results from the combination of improved mechanical properties and retained transport properties, whereas the decrease of the performance at HSE-20 is attributed to the decrease of the ionic conductivity at high LAMP concentrations. These results possibly confirm the combined results obtained by mechanical, conductivity and PFG-NMR measurements, which is that addition of moderate amounts of LAMP can enhance the cycling performance of the polymer electrolytes.

3. Conclusions

The transport properties and local ions dynamics of LAMP-containing HSEs were analyzed by means of impedance spectroscopy and solid-state NMR. The analysis of the admittance/impedance spectra allowed discerning two conductivities, a local conductivity, at timescales so short that no ions accumulation nor Li⁺ transfer across the interphase boundary occur, and a long-range conductivity, at longer timescales, accounting for the contribution of interface resistance and Li⁺ transfer across the particles interface. The former corresponds to the effective conductivity of the HSE, modeled through the Maxwell-Garnett mixing rule, without the contribution of the interface resistance. Overall, this local conductivity is negligibly affected by LAMP, owing to the high intrinsic conductivity of the amorphous and plasticized polymer matrix. On the contrary, the long-range conductivity decreases with increasing volume fraction of LAMP, owing to the high interface resistance for Li⁺ transfer between the two phases. Up to 10 vol% LAMP, the drop in the long-range ionic conductivity can be modeled with the Maxwell-Garnett mixing rule, by considering LAMP particles as insulating. Nonetheless, the contribution of LAMP particles to the overall charge transport process increases with LAMP content and with increasing temperature. Indeed, the additional polarization responsible for the conductivity drop decreases with increasing temperature, especially at high LAMP content. In other words, at high temperatures the long-range conductivity approaches the local conductivity.

Ions' diffusivity was studied by PFG-NMR. Results show a slight decrease of the anions' diffusion coefficient with increasing LAMP concentration, whereas the cations' diffusivity, at least

at high temperatures, is unaffected. This was attributed to the blocking effect of LATP particles towards the anions. Altogether, this results in a moderate increase of the Li^+ transference number, which compensates for the decrease of the total conductivity up to 10 vol% LATP. Nonetheless, this increase of transference number is small and was not confirmed by potentiostatic polarization method.

The occurrence of Li^+ exchange between the two phases was further proved by ^6Li 2D EXSY NMR, which provided an exchange time constant of 50 ms at 60 °C and 20 vol% LATP, and by isotope exchange experiment, coupled with $^6\text{Li}/^7\text{Li}$ NMR, showing almost complete isotope substitution in the electrolyte after galvanostatic cycling between ^6Li -enriched Li discs. Finally, relaxometry experiments and variable temperature NMR experiments indicate negligible variation in the local ions' dynamics, confirming that the local motion is unhindered by the LATP particles and that no anions aggregation occurs on the LATP surface.

Regarding a possible application of the HSEs in Li metal batteries, results of PFG-NMR and conductivity measurements suggest that the transport properties are not affected by addition of moderate amounts of LATP (up to 10% LATP). Mechanical measurements, on the other hand, indicate a clear enhancement of the toughness and Young modulus of the membranes with LATP concentration. The combined results suggest that HSEs with low concentration of LATP (up to 10 vol%) should have improved processability and resistance to dendrites growth. Indeed, this last conclusion was later confirmed by plating/stripping tests in $\text{Li}|\text{Li}$ symmetric cells.

4. Experimental Section

Hybrid Solid Electrolytes Preparation: LATP-based HSEs were prepared by mixing micrometer-sized LATP particles (Schott) with an ethylene oxide-based polymer matrix. LiTFSI (solvionic, 99.9%) was used as lithium salt. The composition of the polymer phase was kept constant, with a mole ratio of ethylene oxide units to Li^+ ($\text{EO}:\text{Li}^+$) fixed at $\text{EO}:\text{Li}^+ = 16$, whereas the content of LATP was varied between 0 and 20 vol% (0, 5, 10 and 20 vol%, corresponding to 0, 12, 22, and 39 wt% of the total HSE mass). The polymer electrolyte matrix was composed of an ethylene oxide-propylene oxide copolymer (p(EO-PO), $M_w \approx 800\,000$), poly(ethylene glycol)dimethyl ether (PEGDME, $M_n \approx 500$, Sigma Aldrich) as plasticizer, and poly(ethylene glycol)diacrylate (PEGDA, $M_n \approx 700$, Sigma Aldrich) as cross-linker. PEGDME with molecular weight of 500 g mol^{-1} was chosen, over lower molecular weight analogues, to enhance the thermal stability of the electrolytes. All HSE components were dried under high vacuum before use, and all preparation steps were carried out in an argon-filled glove box. First, the polymer matrix components, LiTFSI, and the LATP were mixed overnight in acetonitrile (ACN) under vigorous stirring. In a typical preparation, 24 mL of ACN, 1.26 g of p(EO-PO) (25.3 wt% with respect to the total mass of the polymer electrolyte phase), 1.38 g of LiTFSI (27.7 wt%), 0.9 g of PEGDA (18.1 wt%), and 1.44 g of PEGDME (28.9 wt%) were used. Second, AIBN ($\approx 20\text{ mg}$) was added to the solution. The solution was then milled with a Micro Pulverisette 7 premium planetary (Fritsch). Hermetically sealed 45 mL zirconium flasks were used, which were loaded and sealed in argon atmosphere with 5 mm diameter ZrO_2 beads (70 g). The total wet milling time was 20 min at 250 rpm, interrupted by a 10 min pause to avoid overheating of the system. The homogeneous solutions were cast on a Mylar film, with a target dry thickness of 140 μm . The ACN was first evaporated for 3 h at room temperature. Then, the temperature was increased to 70 °C for one hour (half vacuum was applied) for the cross-linking step, forming an interpenetrating acrylic polymer network. Prior to characterization, the membranes were dried under vacuum overnight. The casting was carried out on a minicoater (TOC sheen) in a glove box, under Ar atmosphere,

and the drying steps were carried out in a heated glovebox antechamber. The membranes were finally stored in the same glovebox for further use. The membranes density was measured by weighing discs with diameter of 16 mm and by measuring their thickness with a micrometer.

Characterization Methods: The morphology of the HSEs was studied by SEM, with a FEI Quanta 250. Cross sections were prepared by cutting the membranes at room temperature in an argon glovebox. Images were collected with a voltage acceleration of 10 keV and with a backscattered electron detector (BSED) and with a secondary electron detector. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out under argon (60 mL min^{-1}), from room temperature up to 600 °C, at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, with a TGA 209 F1 Libra (Netzsch). Differential scanning calorimetry measurements (DSC) were performed with a DSC 2500 differential calorimeter (TA Instruments). The measurements were carried out by placing samples of 5–10 mg in sealed aluminum pans under argon atmosphere, in the temperature range between –80 and 100 °C, and with a heating rate of $2\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Each sample was cycled twice between –80 and 100 °C, and the second heating scan was used for the analysis. The mechanical properties of the hybrid electrolytes were characterized by tensile test, with a single column universal testing machine (Instron, 345C-5). The static load cell (100 N 2519 Series S-beam) had a displacement speed of 20 cm min^{-1} . The samples had an approximate length of 4 cm and a width of 10 mm, whereas the separation between the tensile clamps was of $\approx 10\text{ mm}$.

Ionic conductivity measurements were performed with a Solartron 1260A Impedance/Gain-Phase Analyzer, in the frequency range between 32 MHz and 1 Hz (20 points per decade), with a signal amplitude of 20 mV, and in the temperature range between 25 and 70 °C (with $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ step). The measurements were carried out by placing the membranes in coin cells CR2032, with three stainless steel plates of 0.5 mm thickness. The temperature was controlled with a Binder KB23 Cooling incubator. The ionic conductivity was calculated with the following formula

$$\sigma_i = \frac{1}{R_i} \frac{L}{A} \quad (11)$$

where σ_i is the local or long-range conductivity, R_i is the correspondent resistance, as determined by EIS, A is the electrodes surface area, and L is the membrane thickness. The latter was measured with a digital micrometer, after the experiment. The measurement was repeated on three different cells for each composition, and the values of resistance and conductivity used in the analysis are the average values of the three measurements.

Lithium transference number T^+ and salt restricted diffusion coefficient D_{res} were measured in $\text{Li}|\text{Li}$ coin cells, on a Biologic VMP3 potentiostat, at 60 °C. The lithium transference number was determined by potentiostatic polarization method, by combining a chronoamperometry with the measurement of the impedance spectra, collected before and after the chronoamperometry. For the chronoamperometry, a constant voltage of $\pm 10\text{ mV}$ was applied for a duration of 20 min, and the resulting current was registered with a frequency of 10 points s^{-1} during the first minute, and of one point per second during the rest of the chronoamperometry. The impedance spectra were collected in the frequency range between 1 MHz and 100 mHz and with potential amplitude of 10 mV. The experiment was repeated on three cells per sample and six times on each cell, by alternating positive and negative potentiostatic polarization. The cells were allowed to relax for one hour after each chronoamperometric step, and for 10 min after the EIS. The transference number was then calculated using the usual formalism^[61]

$$T_1^+ = \frac{I_{SS}}{I_0} \frac{(\Delta V - R_{int,0}I_0)}{(\Delta V - R_{int,SS}I_0)} \quad (12)$$

where I_0 and I_{SS} are the initial and steady-state current, respectively, ΔV is the applied potential and $R_{int,0}$ and $R_{int,SS}$ are the interface resistances

before and after the chronoamperometric step, respectively. The values of T^+ were further controlled with the following equation^[62]

$$T_2^+ = \frac{R_{b,0}}{(\Delta V / I_{SS} - R_{int,SS})} \quad (13)$$

where $R_{b,0}$ is the bulk resistance before the chronoamperometry. The two calculation methods gave similar results, and the transference numbers reported in the results section are the ones calculated with Equation (12).

The salt restricted diffusion coefficient, D_{res} , was determined using the following equation^[63]

$$D_{res} = -\frac{BL^2}{\pi^2} \quad (14)$$

where B is the slope of the natural logarithm of the cell voltage versus time, during the rest step following the chronoamperometry, and L is the membrane thickness.

Magic angle spinning NMR spectroscopy (MAS NMR) experiments were performed on hybrid solid electrolytes using a Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer equipped with a 2.5 mm probe. The MAS frequency was set to 20 kHz for all measurements except variable temperature studies that were carried out in static samples. ^7Li and ^6Li chemical shifts were referenced to a 1 M LiCl water solution and ^{19}F was referenced indirectly to solid LiF resonating at -204 ppm. 1D experiments were recorded using single excitation pulses (2.4, 3, and 3.7 μs) and relaxation delays of 10, 3, and 8 s for ^7Li , ^6Li , and ^{19}F respectively. These spectra were recorded for qualitative purposes. Saturation recovery experiments were performed to obtain the ^{19}F relaxation times with the relaxation delay varying from 1 ms to 180 s. Variable temperature experiments were conducted in the temperature range of -80 to 110 °C in a static probe, and the ^{19}F 1D experiments were recorded using a single 3 μs excitation pulse with a single scan.

In the Li isotope substitution experiment, a HSE-10 electrolyte with a natural ^6Li abundance (7.5%) was used as electrolyte in a symmetric Li|Li cell, with 99% enriched ^6Li metal. A constant current density of $32 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ was applied to the cell, for 20 h, to force isotope substitution in the electrolyte. The charge passed was calculated to be sufficient to displace all the Li atoms contained in the electrolyte. After the plating, the cell was opened in the glovebox and the electrolyte membrane was carefully removed and packed into a rotor to perform the ^7Li and ^6Li 1D NMR measurements.

Pulsed-field gradient nuclear magnetic resonance (PFG-NMR) was used to determine the diffusion coefficients of ^7Li and ^{19}F for all the electrolytes at variable temperature (ranging from 80 to 20 °C) using a Bruker Avance III 300 MHz wide bore NMR spectrometer equipped with a 5 mm diff50 probe. Stimulated Echo was used for all nuclei diffusion measurements. Typical diffusion time for both nuclei was 25 ms, gradient pulse duration was 2 ms. The maximum field strength was 7.05 T on a log scale.

^7Li and ^{19}F PFG-NMR experiments were repeated for 0 and 20 vol% LATP containing samples to verify whether the obtained diffusion coefficients depend on diffusion time. Bruker Avance NEO 500 MHz wide bore NMR spectrometer equipped with double resonance ($^7\text{Li}/^{19}\text{F}$) 8 mm Diff 50 probe has been used for these experiments. Diffusion time was set to 200 ms, while gradient delay, and the maximum field strength were kept the same as in previous experiments: 2 ms and 7.05 T, respectively.

The same Bruker Avance NEO 500 MHz wide bore NMR spectrometer but with 4 mm MAS probe (maximum spinning speed of 15 kHz) has been used to carry out ^6Li - ^6Li 2D EXSY experiments for 20 vol% LATP sample at 20 and 60 °C. A standard three-pulse sequence with mixing times from 10 ms to 1.6 s and a relaxation delay of 80 s was applied for quantitative characterization of cation exchange between LATP particles and polymer matrix. 16 scans were collected for each of the 64 data points in indirect dimension with the total acquisition time of 23 h per spectrum.

Lithium plating/stripping tests were carried out in symmetrical Li|Li coin cells, at 60 °C. Before each measurement, the cells were kept at 70 °C for 12 h, to ensure stabilization of the lithium interface. The cells were cycled galvanostatically with a fixed plating/stripping capacity of 1 mAh cm^{-2} , and with progressively increasing current densities of 0.05,

0.1, 0.2, 0.33, 0.5, 1 mA cm^{-2} (C/10, C/5, C/3, C/2, C/1), plus one final control cycle at 0.1 mA cm^{-2} (C/10). One cycle was performed at each current density. The measurements were performed in a Neware battery tester.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

composite polymer electrolytes, conduction mechanism, hybrid solid electrolytes, LATP, NASICON, solid-state batteries, transport properties

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